

APPLICATION OF HAMMICK AND ANDREW'S FORMULAE FOR DETERMINING THE PARACHOR OF A SOLUTE.

BY W. V. BHAGWAT AND P. M. TOSHNIWAL.

It is shown that Hammick and Andrew's equation for the parachor of a solute holds under all conditions, *i.e.*, when (a) number of molecules in solution remains equal to the sum of the molecules of the constituents, (b) when they are equal to the solvent molecules only, (c) when they remain equal to solute molecules only, or (d) when there is ionisation. Lakhani and Daroga's modification is proved to be incorrect. In case of salts it is assumed that ionic and atomic parachors are identical. It is further shown that parachor of an associated solute is n times the parachor of simple molecules.

Hammick and Andrew's formula (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754)

$$P_x = (1-x)P_r + xP_s$$

where P_x = is the observed parachor of the solution containing x fraction of solute molecules, P_r = the parachor of the solvent and P_s , the parachor of the solute. The equation has been verified in case of several liquids and solids.

Lakhani and Daroga (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 37, 520) have tried to extend this work to inorganic salts and have advocated a modification of the above formulae on the ground, that when liquids are mixed, the volume is in general equal to the sum of the volumes of the constituents but when a solid is dissolved, the volume change is negligible. Therefore, since according to Sudgen's equation

$$P = V\gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where V is the molecular volume or as in Hammick and Andrew's equation

$$P_x = V_x\gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where V_x is the mean molecular volume, the parachor values calculated by the above equation, when inorganic salts are dissolved in the solvent, will be half as when liquids are dissolved. Consequently Hammick and Andrew's equation when applied to the inorganic solutes in solution and when volume changes are negligible should be written as

$$P_x = (1-x)P_r + x\frac{P_s}{2}$$

These authors have verified this equation in the case of numerous inorganic salts.

The modification introduced by Lakhani and Daroga is, however, open to objection since

(a) The mean molecular weight has nothing to do with volume of the system, but is solely determined by the total weight and total number of molecules.

(b) It is not necessary that for all values of x , the molecular weight calculated according to their suggestion should become double the value obtained by Hammick and Andrew's equation

$$M_m = (1-x)M_r + xM_s$$

where M_m = mean molecular weight, M_r = the molecular weight of the solvent and M_s = the molecular weight of the solute.

(c) As it will be shown below the equation of Hammick and Andrew's remains unchanged whether we assume (i) that total number of molecules after mixing = the sum of the molecules of the constituents, (ii) equal to the number of solvent molecules, and (iii) equal to the number of solute molecules.

(d) The equation also remains unchanged even if we assume that salts ionise, provided ionic and atomic parachors are identified.

Moreover, it appears that they have not verified their equation with actual results. They have substituted a value of 54 for the parachor of water (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1188), which is apparently too high and cannot be justified since the value given by Sudgen is 52.3 ("Parachor", 1930; *vide* also International Critical Table, 1929, IV, 447). They have not found out the value of P_r for themselves. The value for P_r for water as obtained by Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 43) is 52.6. It is clear therefore that to verify their equation, value of P_r should be taken to be 52.3. With this value, we are afraid, their equation completely breaks down as the following table shows.

TABLE I.

Salts.	x .	P_m .	P_x with $P_r = 52.3$.	P_x calc.
KCl	0.0588	53.56	215.2	162.7
KBr	0.0434	55.49	255.2	176.4
KI	0.0368	55.67	288.6	199.4
KNO ₃	0.0426	55.98	276.8	200.9

We have recalculated all their results (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 43) and have observed that the equation completely breaks down.

In case of KClO₃, KBrO₃ and KClO₄ even with $P_r = 54$ the values become absurd (Table II).

TABLE II.

Salt.	x .	P_{Σ} .	P_{Σ} with $P_F=54$ by Lakhani.	P_{Σ} with $P=54$ by Authors.
KClO ₃	0'0216	53'4	218	52'7
KBrO ₃	0'0159	53'19	231'2	7'5
KClO ₄	0'0103	52'86	237'2	—ve

Strangely enough in case of NaNO₃ (*ibid.*, 1938, 16, 520) they have used Hammick and Andrew's equation instead of their own.

They have suggested that in Ray's results (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 16, 43) the observed parachor of ammonium salts approach the calculated value if their equation is employed. But in reality the results so obtained appear to be different as compared to the calculated values.

TABLE III.

NH₄Cl in H₂O.

x .	P_{Σ} .	P_{Σ} with $P_F=54$ Lakhani's equation.	P_{Σ} calc.
0'00662	52'7	Negative	133'6
0'00977	52'97	"	133'6
0'0111	53'28	"	133'6
0'07614	57'79	210	133'6
0'09915	59'40	217	133'6

Hammick and Andrew have derived their equation on the assumption that the total number of molecules in solution remains equal to the sum of the molecules of the constituents. This need not be so. The number of molecules in solution may be equal to that of solute or solvent or may change due to association or dissociation of solute molecules. We shall now consider how far the equation of Hammick and Andrew holds even in these cases.

The Total Molecules in Solution = the Molecules of Solvent.

In this case the solute molecules may be said to distribute themselves equally amongst all the solvent molecules to form new molecules, thus keeping the molecules in solution equal in number to solvent molecules. Hence

if x represents the number of solute molecules distributed per solvent molecule, the weight of the new molecule = weight of one molecule of solvent + weight of x_1 molecules of solute

$$\text{or} \quad M'_n = M_r + x_1 M_s \quad \dots (i)$$

where M'_n = the molecular weight of the new molecules.

In Hammick and Andrew's equation, x represents the number of molecules of solute per $(1-x)$ molecules of solvent. Hence the number of molecules of solute per molecule of solvent = x_1 is given by the relation

$$x_1 = \frac{x}{1-x} \quad \dots (ii)$$

Substituting this value we get

$$M'_n = M_r + \frac{x}{1-x} \cdot M_s \quad \dots (iii)$$

$$\text{or} \quad (1-x)M'_n = (1-x)M_r + xM_s$$

But by Hammick's equation

$$M_n = (1-x)M_r + xM_s$$

$$\text{Hence} \quad (1-x)M'_n = M_n \quad \dots (iv)$$

The value of parachor of the solute P'_n for the new molecule will be given by

$$P'_n = \frac{M'_n}{d} \gamma^{\frac{1}{4}}$$

$$\text{Substituting the value of } M'_n = \frac{M_n}{1-x},$$

$$\text{we get} \quad P'_n = \frac{M_n}{d(1-x)} \gamma^{\frac{1}{4}}$$

$$\text{But} \quad P_n = \frac{M_n}{d} \gamma^{\frac{1}{4}}$$

$$\text{Hence} \quad P'_n = \frac{P_n}{1-x}$$

This value will be = $2P_n$ if $x = \frac{1}{2}$; and not for all values of x as suggested by Lakhani and Daroga. The parachor of the new molecule is given by the equation

$$P'_n = P_r + x_1 P_s$$

if parachor is an additive property and therefore equal to parachor of one molecule of solvent + x molecules of solute. Substituting the values of P'_x and x_1 we get

$$\frac{P_x}{1-x} = P_r + \frac{x}{1-x} P_x$$

or

$$P_x = (1-x)P_r + xP_x.$$

Thus the equation of Hammick and Andrew remains unchanged and and hence gives the correct values of P'_x . In a similar way it can be shown without difficulty that Hammick and Andrew's equation holds good when the total molecules = molecules of solute, and also when solute ionises.

The nature of the expression when solute molecules undergo association is discussed below.

When Solute Molecules Associate.

Let us now suppose that solute associates, so that n molecules form one molecule.

$$nA = (A)_n.$$

If x be the fraction of the number of these associated molecules then mean molecular weight

$$M'_x = (1-x_1)M_r + x_2M'_n,$$

where M'_x is the molecular weight of the associated molecule of the solute. Hence $M'_x = nM_n$.

If the original fractions of the solvent molecule to solute molecules without polymerisation are as $1-x : x$ then there are $\frac{x}{1-x}$ molecules of solute per molecule of solvent. Hence the number of associated molecules formed is $\frac{x}{n(1-x)}$. Thus the fraction of the associated molecule

$$x_1 = \frac{x/n(1-x)}{1 + \frac{x}{n(1-x)}}$$

$$x_1 = \frac{x}{n - (n-1)x}$$

Substituting this value we get

$$\begin{aligned} M'_n &= \left\{ \frac{n(1-x)}{n-(n-1)x} \right\} M_r + \frac{x}{n-(n-1)x} M'_x \\ &= \frac{n}{n-(n-1)x} \{ (1-x)M_r + xM_x \} \\ &= \frac{n}{n-(n-1)x} M_n. \end{aligned}$$

Also
$$P'_n = \frac{M'_n}{d} \cdot \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{nM_n}{n-(n-1)x} \cdot \frac{\gamma^{\frac{1}{2}}}{d} = \frac{nP_n}{n-(n-1)x}.$$

But
$$P'_n = (1-x_2)P_r + x_2P'_x$$

or
$$\frac{P_n \cdot n}{n-(n-1)x} = \frac{n(1-x)}{n-(n-1)x} P_r + \frac{x}{n-(n-1)x} P'_x$$

where P'_x is the parachor of the associated molecule

or
$$nP_n = n(1-x)P_r + xP'_x$$

or
$$xP'_x = n x P_x \quad \text{but this is} \\ = n \{ P_n - (1-x)P_r \}$$

or
$$P'_x = nP_x.$$

Parachor of associated molecule, provided it is additive, is n times the parachor of a simple molecule. This means it is impossible to detect association of solute by parachor, since in mean molecular weight the value to be substituted for M is n times M . The failure of Hammick and Andrew's formulae therefore must be attributed to some other cause than mentioned above.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
HOLEKAR COLLEGE, INDORE.

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